

Teacher Education in India: Issues and Concerns in Present Scenario

Dr. Waseem Zahra

Assistant Professor

Department of B.Ed., B.N.K.B. P.G. College, Akbarpur, Ambedkarnagar, U.P., India

Email Id: waseemzahra85@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Over the last half century and especially in the last decades teaching learning has been under gone drastic changes. There has been a shift towards student centred classroom from teachers centred classroom and teacher's role become more as facilitator of learning rather than an autocratic master. In the view of current changes in the social, cultural, economic and political environment, the radical change is essential in the teacher education so that teachers could raise their standard with the changing needs of the society. In the present, the unexpected growth in a large number of non-government teacher training institutions has deteriorated the quality of the teaching programme. It is observed that non-government institutions lack of adequate physical infrastructure and produce a large number of incompetent teachers. Many other problems like the ratio between demand and supply of teachers, the poor standard methods of teaching, traditional curriculum, the problem of supervision, inadequate empirical research, poor infrastructure, etc. has also aroused. Keeping in consideration all these problems and concern, the educationists, policy makers, curriculum planners, and other stakeholders need to reconstruct and reform the teacher education programme for the growth and development of teachers as well as for the nation. The Present paper discusses about the meaning, need, significance, issues and solutions of teacher education.

Keywords: Teacher Education, meaning, significance, issues, suggestions

Introduction:

Education has great importance in building strong and developed societies, and it is considered as a important tool for bringing positive change in the social, political, economic and cultural life of people. The whole process o teaching-learning is shaped by many important agents, and the teacher is one of them. The teacher is claimed to play a pivot role in education. Teachers can craft or blight a nation. Teaching is a fine art, which needs to be practiced through the proper training, acquisition of various skills, competencies and relevant knowledge about the learner and the subject matter in the contemporary world. The Kothari Commission (1964-66) stated that "a sound programme of professional education of teachers is essential for the qualitative improvement of education." It highlighted that investment in teacher education can yield very rich dividends because the financial resources required are small when measured against the resulting improvements in the education of millions. The Commission emphasised that

training and orientation of teacher is very important so that he understands and accomplishes his changing role effectively.

Meaning of Teacher Education:

Teacher Education refers to the policies, procedures and provision designed to equip pupil teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school and wider community. Those professionals who engage in this activity are called Teacher educators or, in some contexts, teacher trainers. Now a days teaching-learning process is going through tremendous change and teacher education is playing important role in the education world. The teacher training program is helpful for teachers in improving their efficiency, ability, knowledge, professionalism and motivation for their work.

Significance of Teacher Education:

There is a tremendous change in today's generation, technology, and environment as compared to earlier. For this evolving environment, it is required that the teachers must be updated, to get better teaching results. Teaching and learning are always like two parallel lines that are bound to go together. It is always seen that students of well-informed and skilled teachers are better than the other students. Therefore, teachers must get training at regular intervals of time for updated knowledge regarding the ever-changing environment. To face the new challenges and changes in the educational world, the Teacher Education is helping Teachers around the globe. Here are some points about the significance of Teacher Education–

- Today's children look at electronic gadgets more than books. They prefer learning online rather than offline. So, the teaching training is useful in teaching teachers how to use electronic gadgets to encourage students to study, like giving assignments online or taking tests online.
- The Teacher Education also teaches teachers how to study student's psychology. If there are any problems, they sometimes need to become emotional or career counsellors.
- Teacher Education will help improve teachers in their teaching methods, time management, technical knowledge, motivating students, teaching skills. This resulting in the overall improvement in the institution.
- Teachers can help students in applying academic knowledge in solving their daily life problems.
- Teachers are taught long-lasting skills and a better way of teaching. They are also trained how to conduct knowledge-based activities for students like quizzes, debates, group discussions, etc.
- The program also taught teachers how they can increase the vocabulary of the students in the classroom so that the students become better communicators.

- In distancing learning courses also, the Teacher Education helps the teacher how to use technology and digital communication tools for better teaching results.

Problems of Teacher Education in India:

In the contemporary situation, a huge number of teachers are untrained. In some areas, the situation is not very hopeful. It has been noticed that teacher educators are neither professionally qualified nor committed to their profession. The quality in pre-service education has shown the worsening condition. While Sharma (2015) emphasized the need for ICT in the professional growth of the teacher and determining the global economy. The rise in substandard institutions of teacher education is the cause of such emerging problems and mismanagements. The National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education: Towards Preparing Professional and Humane Teacher (NCFTE, 2009) expressed concern over the quality of teacher education. Though, National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has taken quality improvement in teacher education, the system is still not fulfilling the essential need of providing competent and committed teachers after completing the initial teacher training programmes. A huge number of teacher training institutions are not following the instruction and guidelines of NCTE. At present, the radical change in the organization of curriculum, use of modern technologies and more emphasis on advanced and creative practices are necessity of the period. Thus, teacher education has to be transformed and reoriented today. Some of major problems and concerns prevailing in the teacher education system are following:

Selection Procedure:

A continuing problem of the pre-service teacher training programme is to select the high-quality aspirants and to refuse admission to those who do not have aptitude and commitment to the teaching profession. The main goal of the teacher education is to identify the candidates who exhibit the personal attributes (sincerity, honesty, potentiality, commitment, impartiality and neutrality). In-depth knowledge of subject, psychology and pedagogy lead to successful learning outcomes. The problem arises when those candidates enter this programme who do not have necessary competencies and qualities required for such an important profession. This results in the production of poor-quality teachers in the education system. Thus, it is need of the hour to evolve and sound procedure which can help in a suitable selection of persons who are likely to become efficient teachers.

Issue Related to Quality:

In the ongoing time, the quality concern in the field of education has emerged as a great problem in the time of globalization and privatization. The present teacher training programme is designed in such a manner that it does not provide the proper opportunities to trainee to develop essential teaching skills. According to Anees (2015) "despite realizing various measures still, numerous problems of teachers training exist in India. The main problem of the present teacher education system has been identified 'the

unproductive trained teachers. Skill and proficiency development aspect is most neglected. The practice teaching aspect is not done according to the need and demand of the trainees. For the teaching of theory, part consumes almost 70% time and practice teaching 30% of the total time available. This situation arises because the organizers of teacher's training programme are not aware of the present problems of schools.

Traditional Curriculum:

The National Teacher Education Curriculum needs to be in accordance with the curriculum framework for school education. A teacher needs to be prepared to fulfil the requirements and demands of the school education and the learners and the learning process. Therefore, it is essential that the curriculum should be organised as per the ongoing demands of the school and society as well as for the nation. Khan (2016) emphasized on 'the need for significant transformation of the curriculum strategies and methods used in teaching.' In the present day, the teacher training institutions are followed the traditional method for teacher training programmes without bringing the essential modifications with needs of the trainee.

Problem of Teacher Readiness for Inclusive Classrooms:

According to the Official Estimate of the Census of India (2011) data on disability about 2.21% of the total population are people with disabilities (PWD) in India. There are many problems in teaching children with special needs in regular classrooms. These problems arise due to lack of proper infrastructure, material resources lack of proper training and undesirable attitudes of teachers. There is an urgent requirement to equip teachers to handle the problems of segregation prevailing in schools. Das, Kuyini & Desai (2013) studied the current skill levels of regular primary and secondary school teachers in Delhi, in order to teach students with disabilities in inclusive education settings. They found that about 70% of the regular school teachers had neither received training in special education nor had any experience teaching students with disabilities.

Lack of Professional Development:

The outdated approach to teaching is prevailing in schools among older teachers who were taught and have been teach in these traditional approaches. Continuous Professional Development is essentially required for the success of the different teaching approaches. In order to give teachers, the opportunity of sound professional development along with content & methodology, there is an urgent requirement to integrate emotional capabilities and life skills with individual development, continuing education, in-service education, curriculum writing, and peer collaboration etc.

Occupational Stress among Teachers:

In the era of science and technology, fast and busy life has made the teaching profession physically and mentally very problematic. The teacher needs a lot of potentialities to deal with classroom situations and professional work. Sometimes, the teacher comes under

stress due to growing pressure. According to Eysenck (2001) "stress occurs when the perceived demands of a situation exceed the individual's perceived ability to handle those demands." Occupational stress also affects the professional growth of teachers. Occupational stress takes place when there is a disparity between the demand of the environment and an individual's capability to carry out a task. The major causes for stress among teachers are excessive working hours, less handsome salary, excessive workload, changes in curriculum and courses, rising class sizes, changes to assessment and, lack of job security etc.

Lack of Training in Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

In the modern era, information and communication technology (ICT) is one of the best tools to achieve access, inclusion, and quality in teacher education. The use of ICT in obtaining knowledge and skills has become an essential pre-requisite in teacher education. But there are some problems which are prevailing in our education system. Lack of infrastructure and equipment results in one of the major issues of present teacher education courses that the teacher trainees are not getting proper training in the information and communication technology (ICT). They do not know how to use ICT for facilitating their teaching-learning process. Even the teacher educators themselves lack in necessary ICT skills.

Less Focus on Research and Innovations:

According to Kumar & Azad (2016) the quality researches have been considerably neglected in the area of teacher education. The sufficient amounts of researches are not being conducted and not as per global standards. It has been observed that researches are conducted without keeping in mind the current issues and challenges of teacher education programmes. It results in no significant transformation in the existing educational system. There is an essential to develop the national arrangement for research in alignment with the local and national level priorities.

Lack of proper Infrastructures:

It is definitely very crucial to have adequate physical facilities in terms of material for providing sound professional training. Chauhan, (2004) stated that "it is the combination of several components such as knowledgeable teacher educators, good classrooms, library and laboratories which make good teacher education institute". According to Khan, Fauzee & Daud, (2016) the teacher training colleges suffer from inadequate physical facilities, classrooms, laboratories, libraries and Information & Communication Technology (ICT) facilities which do not have updated quality books and overall environment is not conducive. The most important problem is that a large number of teacher training institutions do not have experimental schools attached to them. So, it results in the difficulty of carrying out the practice teaching task of trainees effectively.

Suggestions:

- Proper selection technique should be developed for selecting the proper candidate for the teacher-learning process. The selection process for admission in teacher education should be updated in such a manner that the only those aspirants can get admission who have teaching aptitude and commitment to the teaching profession.
- The teacher training programme should be developed in such a way that it provides sufficient opportunities to pupil teachers to develop their essential professional skills. It will help prospective pupil-teachers in their training to develop an all-round personality and making them competent enough to teach the learners.
- The pupil teachers should be trained in such a way so that they can deal with the 'Children with Special Needs' along with the normal students in the comprehensive and inclusive classrooms. Inclusive education should be made an integral part of the teacher education curriculum.
- Professional development of teacher educators is a continuous process. Therefore, New Refresher Course, Orientation Programmes, Workshops, Symposium and short-term courses should be encouraged on a frequent basis for the professional development of teacher educators. For the growth of professional temperament, the teacher training institution should be sufficiently furnished with facilities for start-up various types of activities such as refresher course, orientation programmes, workshops, symposium and short-term courses, daily assembly programmes, social work and other co-curricular activities.
- Teacher educators need to learn various skills like meditation and yoga to maintain the balance between professional life and personal life. The practice of meditation helps in relieving the stressful mind and save them from occupational stress.
- The teacher education departments should give more opportunity to conducting researches on teacher education, curriculum developments and evaluation procedure. Various induction programmes and exchange programmes with different universities within India and abroad should be sponsored by the government so that teachers can improve their quality.
- Teacher educators need to be updated with advance technology taking place in the area of education. Pupil teachers should be taught the art of using information & communication technology (ICT) in the classroom to facilitate better teaching-learning process.
- It should be confirmed that the teacher training institutions have appropriate infrastructure for teacher training. NCTE should supervise the existing condition so that necessary action can be taken against such teacher training institutions if they have not required infrastructure.

- NCTE should supervise the private teacher training institutions to stop them merely the platform of money making. Strict action should be taken against those teacher training institutions which are involved in commercialization and profit-orientation of education.
- The Central Government and the State Governments should recruit good quality teacher educators to solve the problem of unequal ratio of demand and supply in teacher education.
- The curriculum for teacher training programme should be reorganised from time to time according to changing demand and latest developments of the society, nation, profession and globalized world. Advance research should be conducted to evaluate the course structure. The findings of such advance researches can be beneficial for assessing, evaluating and designing the curriculum of teacher education.

Conclusion:

Education helps in establishing a society which appreciates peace and stability and moves towards progress and improvement. It is a procedure which encourages the innovative capability of an individual and supports him to concentrate his energies on the points he wants to fulfil. A nation becomes rich not by riches person but rather by its educated citizens. The teacher is the vital point of the entire education system and the primary agent for bringing desirable changes in the teaching-learning process. Thus, quality teachers are important factors in attaining sustainable global development. As no education system can rise above the existing level without the quality of its teachers, vigorous efforts would be needed to bring substantial reforms. Therefore, their training, recruitment, retention, status and working conditions should be among global priorities today. But the shortage of well-trained teachers is a significant problem today. To fill this gap, the central government, regulatory bodies like NCTE, UGC and other statutory bodies like NCERT, NUEPA, IASE, Central Universities, and policy planners with other stakeholders have to play a major role in this process of reform. The restructuring curriculum of teacher training programme needs to be revised according to the changing demand of the society and nation. To conclude, proper training, positive attitude and professionalism needs to be instilled in each and every phase of teacher education starting from conceptualisation to evaluation and appraisal to prepare teachers and improve the quality of education.

References:

- Anees, A. (2015). Teacher education and their problems. *International Journal of Academic Research in Education and Review*, 3(1), 1-6.
- Das, A. K., Kuyini, A. B., & Desai, I. P. (2013). Inclusive education in India: Are the teachers prepared? *International Journal of Special Education*, 28(1), 27-36.

- Desai, A. J. (2011). Problems of teacher education in India. *International Journal for Research in Education*, 1(1), 54-58.
- Khan, F., Fauzee, O., & Daud, Y. (2016). Teacher training, problems and the challenges: a comparative study between India and Pakistan. *Journal of Research*, 2, 1-12.
- Chauhan, C.P.S. (2004). *Modern Indian Education: Policy progress and problems*. New Delhi, Retrieved from <http://opac.cus.ac.in/cgi-bin/koha/opac-detail.pl>, biblionumber 145889.
- Eysenck, M.W. (2001). *Simply Psychology*. UK, Psychology Press, 61-75. Retrieved from <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9781003100492/simply-psychology-michael-eysenck>.
- Kumar, P. & Azad, S. (2016). Teacher education in India: Some policy issues and challenges. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Research*, 2(6), 1217-1224.
- National Council for Teacher Education. (2009). *National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education Towards Preparing Professional and Humane Teacher*. New Delhi, India. Retrieved from https://ncte.gov.in/website/PDF/NCFTE_2009.pdf
- Sharma, H. K. (2015). Role of ICT in improving the excellence of education. *International Journal of Computer Science and Engineering (IJCSE)*, 8(7), 78-81.